

ASSESSMENT OF VALUES EDUCATION STRATEGIES IMPLEMENTATION AND INTERNALIZATION IN SECONDARY SCHOOLS IN ABIA STATE, NIGERIA

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Abstract:

The study investigated the extent to which research supported values education strategies are implemented as well as the degree of internalization of these values among public secondary school students in Abia State. The study adopted the descriptive survey design and covered 235 public secondary schools. The population comprised the SSII students (6,390) and their teachers (3735). Stratified sampling was used to select the ten sample schools and sample subjects making a total of 957. Five research questions guided the study while researcher constructed instrument titled "Values Education Strategy Implementation and Internalization Assessment Questionnaire (VESIAQ) was validated and the reliability calculated using test-retest method. The instrument had the reliability of 0.68 and was administered to the samples. The data collected was analysed using mean scores and standard deviations. The findings revealed that out of the fourteen researches supported values education strategies only one was utilized by the teachers. The findings further revealed that out of the three values assessed for their internalization only one seemed effective with the current method. It was recommended that there should be a complete overhaul of the strategy of implementation of values education in order to achieve the desired objectives on the students. The teachers should therefore be made to attend workshops where these strategies would be available to them.

Keywords: values education strategies, implementation, internalization, honesty, compassion, respect

1. Introduction

Values are generally long-term standards or principles that are used to judge the worth of an idea or action. They provide the criteria by which one decides whether something

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is good or bad, right or wrong (UNESCO, 2010). Values education is the process by which people give moral values to others. Wikipedia (2017) defined it as the process that gives young people an initiation into values, giving knowledge of the rules needed to function in the mode of relating to other people. It went further to state that values education seeks the development in the student a grasp of certain underlying principles, together with the ability to apply the rules intelligently and the disposition to do so. Robb (2008), Lovat and Toomey (2007) expressed values education as a process of teaching and learning about the ideas that a society deems important.

The concept values education are sometimes used as an umbrella of concepts that includes moral education and citizenship education. However all these can be broken down into, character, moral development, religious education, spiritual development, citizenship education, personal development, social development and cultural development. Hence, Berkowitz (2011) pointed out that all these nomenclatures are a matter of semantics that mean one and the same thing.

For the purpose of this paper, values education can therefore be defined as the formal internalization of societal ideas that promote positive effective behavior and prevent response to undesirable behavior by the student. In this paper values education and character education was treated as the same thing and were used interchangeably.

1.1 Why values education

All societies are struggling to reduce all forms of criminalities perpetuated by its citizens ranging from assaults, thefts, vandalism, kidnapping, hate speeches, cultism, terrorism and many others. The society also wants to reduce the damage young people cause themselves and the pain they cause parents and the society through indecent behaviours such as drug abuse, early sexual activities, disrespect to constituted authorities and others. There is therefore a desperate need to seek radical changes in the society. Currently it is obvious that the methods in use do not seem to be working. Consequently, many researchers have strongly raised the issue of values education without which the safer and more pleasant society desired will not be achieved (Bill, 2009, DeNobile and Hogan, 2014).

Values education is the attempt within schools to craft pedagogies and supportive structures to foster the development of positive, ethical, pro-social inclinations and competences in youth including around strengthening their academic focus and achievement.

Values education can take place in any organization such as educational institutions, families or in the communities. It involves older people in a position of authority or who are more experienced making those underlying their own behavior more explicit in order to assess the effectiveness of these values and associated behavior for their own and others' long-term wellbeing.

1.2 Values education strategies

DeNobile and Hogan (2009) identified three levels of values and the strategies of implementation. These are community, school and classroom levels respectively.

At the classroom level students engage in a variety of activities designed to make them more aware of certain values and how they apply to everyday life in an out of school. The activities range from discussions based on moral dilemmas through to philosophical activities to analysis of media and communication to reveal underlying value messages. A code of ethic can be provided for the students to live by and perhaps develop orally.

At the school level, values are taught directly and indirectly as a result of school history, background or religious affiliation.

This obviously influences the shape of the curriculum and the pedagogy at the classroom level. It also transforms the way the people think, act and live in the world. For instance school 'A' can produce students who combine spiritual maturity with academic excellence and rounded social and physical development while school 'B' may decide to produce people of competence, conscience and compassion.

Berkowitz (2011) identified fifteen categories of educational practices as having a research base that supports their effectiveness in fostering the development of character. These fifteen categories of educational strategies comprise an eclectic mix of specific pedagogical methods (e.g. moral dilemma discussions), specific parenting strategies that can be applied in schools (e.g. induction), broader categories of classroom and school practices (e.g. service to others and other educational processes that support character education (e.g. professional development). These set of trainable teacher practices and school implementation principles are directed by what the existing research supports and are listed below;

- 1) Cooperative learning;
- 2) Moral dilemma discussion;
- 3) Service to others;
- 4) Developmental discipline;
- 5) Role modeling and mentoring;
- 6) Nurturance;
- 7) Trust and trustworthiness;
- 8) High expectations;
- 9) School-wide character focus;
- 10) Family/community involvement;
- 11) Pedagogy of empowerment;
- 12) Teaching about character;
- 13) Teaching social-emotional competences;
- 14) Induction;
- 15) Professional development (Berkowitz, 2011).

Peer interactive strategies are at the core of effective character education pedagogy and require students talking to each other. Berkowitz and Bier (2005) found peer interactive strategies to be prevalent in effective character education programme. Cooperative learning is a form per-interactive pedagogy in which students work in small groups. Moral dilemma discussions are designed to stimulate the development of moral reasoning. It typically entails teacher facilitating classroom discussions of open-

ended moral dilemma with the focus on stimulating peer-to-peer cognitive grappling with apparent disagreements about how to resolve moral problems. From a cognitive development stand points, Keimer, Paolitto and Hersh in Berkowitz (2011) pointed out that moral dilemma discussions strategy was intended to promote cognitive disequilibrium and hence cognitive development. Research has demonstrated the effectiveness of moral dilemma discussion in fostering moral reasoning development across a wide range of ages and contexts (Berkowitz, 1985).

In terms of service to others, it is argued that by serving other students both discover the intrinsic value of moral service and develop more moral values, habits and virtues. This can be deduced from the students participating in community service. For instance there are two categories of service that take place in educational setting, community service and service learning. The former is done to serve the needs of others while the later involves applying the curricular learning to enhance service or by learning the curricular through service (Berkowitz and Bier, 2005). Billig (2002) posits that service learning has positive impacts on academic achievement and character development.

Behavior management is one of the controversial challenges in education. This has to do with how to promote positive effective behavior and how to prevent or respond to undesirable behavior such as disruptive and anti-social behaviours. Behaviourists have always relied on rewards and punishment but developmental discipline focuses on building relationships, empowering students, induction that is engaging the students on critical discussions of behavior and its consequences as well as relevant consequences as a means of preventing and responding to undesirable behavior (Watson 2008, Bear 2005). Its focus is not on the immediate cessation of a specific behavior but the long-term development of more desirable and effective behavior choices.

Role modeling mentoring involves adults, older students or community members. This is based on the relationship between the mentor and mentee, whereby the positive relationship that develops with the older student or adult leads to modeling of the mentor's character strength. This builds upon the research in the power of positive modeling by parents on children's character development (Lickona, 2008).

Baumrind (2008) noted that from parenting literature nurture (love, care, positive regard etc) has a very wide range of positive developmental effects on children. The teacher and the school show love and care to stimulate the child to love and care (Gregory, Cornell, Fan, Sheras, Shih and Huang, 2010).

Trust is a cognitive and affective evaluation of another. Trustworthiness refers to the characteristics of an individual such as consistency, integrity, transparency and benevolence that leads others to trust him or her. Watson in Berkowitz (2011) noted that trust is at the core of developmental discipline. Bryk and Schneider (2002) discovered in their study that a culture of trust among the adults working in a school is critical to the school success. Therefore, the students need to be trustworthy and to learn to trust others.

In terms of setting high expectations, research suggests that effective character education actually sets high expectations for both academic achievement and behavior (Berkowitz, 2011). Deducing from the research on the effects of parenting on child development, it is clear that parents who set high behavior expectations for their children have children who are more morally mature in a variety of ways (Baumrind, 2008). This can be achieved through setting clear expectations, checking in on progress, allowing multiple attempts at success offering constructive feedback and allowing play relevant to the task among other factors (Urban, 2008).

Values education need to have a school-wide focus in two central ways if it is to be optimally successful. First, it should be a core aspect of the school's authentic mission and vision (Elbot and Fulton, 2008). It should not be made second class to academic achievement. Secondly, there should be a school-wide character education events and practices (Berkowitz and Bier, 2005). Effective character education practices in schools identified by Lickona in Berkowitz (2011) include morning whole school assemblies, school wide after school events that focus on character, school wide service projects and school wide moratorium days for study of ethical issues among other practices.

Berkowitz and Bier (2005) found that effective character education programmes encourage parental and community involvement. Consequently, parents as clients should partner with the school in designing, implementing and or evaluating character education.

One of the tenets of effective value education resonates with constructive education and citizenship education such as student empowerment. The results of the Research of Reevea Halusic (2009) on self-determinant theory supports the developmental power of authoritative (supportive, nurturing, empowering) school climate which tend to foster greater academic achievement and character development. Studies such as the Child Development Project relies heavily on empowering class meetings where students solve problem, make decisions and plan events (Development Studies, 1996).

In teaching social-emotional competencies, schools need to be intentional and comprehensive in implementing values education and ultimately in fostering the development of character in students (Beland, 2003). Berkowitz (2011) pointed out that teaching about character in the absence of a school climate that embodies explicit set of character goals, integrated character concepts into the character curriculum, supplementary character education curricular or teachable movements such as behavior incidents, and current events in the class will not be effective. Berkowitz (2011) pointed out that the field of social-emotional learning (SEL) and the collaborative for academic, social and emotional learning provide extensive resource, including empirical research to support the effectiveness of teaching social and emotional competences in short on both academic achievement and character development. Berkowitz & Bier (2005) asserted that without SEL competences students will not be adequately prepared to learn and grow. Consequently, schools need to support directly the learning and development necessary for functioning in social contexts.

Induction has positive impact on children's moral development in families and therefore has parallels in teacher behavior (Berkowitz & Grych 1998, Wentzel, 2002). This is clearly related to developmental discipline (Watson, 2003) and as was earlier mentioned is exploited in the education of values.

Professional development is not a practice that focuses directly on students. It focuses more on academic instruction than a value education and will not be applied in this study.

In Abia State, the subject close to values education at the junior secondary level is referred to as Religion and National Values Education. The subject is made up of Religion and Mora Studies, Social Studies and Security Education. All these sub-topics are in one textbook. In this book values education form two chapters of barely twenty five pages in all in a book of fifteen chapters. Each topic is presented as an academic matter that should be memorized and regurgitated. Topics are made up of lists of characteristics of a value, the consequences or the benefits. Topics covered are inadequate but include honesty, cooperation, self-reliance, nurture, integrity, contentment, discipline and courage.

The umbrella concepts of values education earlier mentioned can further be broken down to various constructs such as compassion, respect, honesty, sense of duty, commitment, perseverance including those in the textbooks of JSI. But for the purpose of this study only compassion, honesty and respect will be assessed.

Compassion is helping those who are hurting and it begins with sympathy which is seeing someone's pain. It involves a student noticing a fellow student who has hurt himself or herself. It is also being concerned about a colleague or even a stranger who need help. Compassion creates a feeling of duty, responsibility and sometimes urgency to help find a remedy. Compassion is therefore doing something to relieve someone's pain. It is not enough to see someone in need and feel bad especially for those hurting, one need to do something. Compassion is one of the values held in high esteem all over the world. Fien (2003) noted that compassion does not necessarily mean emotional willingness to enter into another's feeling and express sympathy and solidarity it also involves the active will to share and help alleviate the plight of others. Clouston (2007) pointed out that as values are subjective and affective, it requires the learning environment to not only produce critical thinking and the development of professional competences but to facilitate personal growth and change within students at cognitive, emotional and spiritual levels in which compassion is one. She and Chef Bower in Fien (2003) noted that this dimensions are frequently ignored in education which is very challenging. She further proffered that there is need to build a curriculum that supports students to understand, reflect on and restructure their own caring values in order to develop the ability to put others before their own self interests. This implies that students should develop the skills to challenge others in situations where caring values are not achieved and sustained. This makes the proper teaching of values such as compassion very important in Abia State public secondary school in order to achieve a peaceful and safe society consequently the need to assess the level of internalization of compassion by these students.

Honesty is being truthful, telling the truth at all times, playing by the rule, no cheating, not exaggerating the facts, admitting when wrong and avoiding the urge to take things that do not belong to you. (Character of first education 2017) Berko (2017) in a study noted that honesty and respect are priorities to college students compared to other moral values but the trouble is if they do consistently act on them. This assertion is a good evidence to support the need for the assessment of internalization of these values in the students to ensure that the value education offered was not an exercise in futility. The assessment will not only indicate whether the students characters have been moulded around the value of honesty but also whether the method applied was effective.

Respect is treating others with honour and dignity. Everyone has worth and dignity as a human being, whether young or old, rich or poor, male or female irrespective of ethnic nationality or any other difference. This is the reason why people should be treated with honour, dignity, courtesy instead of bullying, harassing or manipulating in order to get what they want (Character First Education, 2017). You should also show respect to those counting on you by being responsible, diligent and thorough. Self-respect is also important as it means that you should recognize your own worth as a human being and avoid anything that will damage your mind, body or integrity. The implication is that you must be consistent in your actions no matter the pressure. If all these values, compassion, honesty and respect are found embedded in the minds and shown in the actions of these secondary school students the society would be a better place for the current generation.

In the current methods of implementation, there is no room for internalization through discussing real life cases or hypothetical cases where the students will be fully involved and proffer the consequences or benefits. The teaching of these topics are purely academic and are not geared towards the effective domain as well. The assessment of these values are purely cognitive only since they take only exams in them. It should also be affective which should be practicalised since the objective is to change the students positively. Teaching and learning in terms of values education in this case seem to be defeated.

At the senior secondary level, Christian religion is taught along with civic education. Christian religion interspersed with moral implications is supposed to take care of values education. On the other hand, parents and communities are never involved to assist. The involvement of the parents and communities which is expected to help the teachers understand the students' events in the class or school are never exploited. The implication is that values education is not given its right place if the objectives of teaching it at that level are to make some positive impact in the life of the students at the young age. For a peaceful and safer society, there is therefore the need to assess the strategies applied in the implementation of values education and the internalization of these values by the students to see whether progress has been made or there should be a change in strategy.

2. The Problem

Considering the growing prevalence of criminality in secondary schools in Abia State which include cultism, violence, assaults, vandalism against teachers and fellow students, theft and many others, moral values seem to be fast eroded in the secondary school in Abia State. Although Civic Education is taught in secondary schools a comprehensive values education has never been fully and formally integrated into the secondary schools curriculum as is obtained in the developed world like United States, Australia, France, United Kingdom and others. All societies are struggling to reduce all forms of criminality at this level and encourage responsible behavior in order to create super and pleasant society. This effort seems to be lacking in the education industry in Abia State consequently the students just drift along without concrete values education. This has made these secondary school easy recruits for cultism and unruly behavior by misguided elements from the tertiary institutions.

This paper seeks to assess first the values education strategies applied in its implementation and secondly the current degree of internalization of values education no matter how little possessed by these students in order to determine the urgency of the need to change strategy in handling values education in Abia State secondary schools. The paper will focus on honesty, compassion and respect being some of the key universal values.

2.1 Research Questions

- 1) To what extent has the teaching of values education in Abia State followed research supported strategies?
- 2) What is the degree of internalization of values education in terms of honesty among secondary school students in Abia State?
- 3) What is the degree of internalization of values education in terms of compassion among secondary school students in Abia State?
- 4) To what extent is compassion internalized by Abia State secondary school students through values education?

3. Methodology

The study adopted a descriptive survey design, since none of the variables were manipulated. The study population comprised 6,390 Junior Secondary II (JSS II) students and 3,735 teachers from 235 schools in the three education zones of Ohafia, Aba and Umuahia. The JS II students were selected because they can at least read and write and are not external examination class that does not need distraction.

The teachers were selected because they are in close contact with the students daily and can attest to their daily conduct. Stratified sampling was used to select 10 schools from each of the zones. Considering the large size of the population the advice of Seymour Sudman on minimum sample size of 20-50 for each subgroup was applied (Gall, Gall & Borg, 2007) for this study, 20 was employed. Stratified sampling was also

applied in the selection of the sample subjects in order to get adequate representation from the three zones.

Twenty teachers and students each were selected from each of the 10 sample schools in the three zones. This gave a total of 1,200 sample subjects.

3.1 Research Instrument

The instrument developed that was administered on the samples was titled “Values Education Strategy, Implementation and Internalization Assessment Questionnaire (VESIIAQ)”. It comprised of four sections and these were: biographical section, value education strategy implementation, honesty values, compassion values and respect values. Each section has responses ranging from very low extent to very high extent where the very low extent is 1 point and very high extent 4 points.

3.2 Validation and Reliability

The content, construct and face validity of the instrument were carried out. The instrument was also given to some experts in the area of evaluation and psychology to validate the instrument. The experts made necessary corrections and suggestions that improved the instrument. A pilot study was conducted on the teachers, principals and students who were not in the sample schools. A test re-test was used to test the reliability of the developed instrument. The reliability value was 0.68.

3.3 Administration of the Instrument

The instrument was administered on the respondents through three research assistants. Prior to this, the researcher sought consent of the various heads of the schools who incidentally are also participants in the study. The consents were given. One thousand two hundred copies of the questionnaires were distributed to the sample subjects in the three education zones with the help of the research assistants. Nine hundred and fifty seven (957, 79.8%) of the questionnaires were retrieved, scored and analyzed.

3.4 Method of Data Analysis

The data collected on the three posited research questions were analyses with the use of weighted means and standard deviations. Any mean value above 2.50 was accepted as high degree while those that fell below 2.50 were termed low degree and were rejected.

4. Results and Discussion

4.1 Research Question 1: To what extent are research supported strategies applied in implementing values education in Abia State public secondary schools?

Table 1: Mean scores of respondents on the use of research supported strategies to implement values education in Abia State public secondary schools

S/N	Items	X	SD	Decision
	To what extent are these strategies used to implement values education in Abia State secondary schools			
1	Cooperative learning	0.90	0.75	Very low extent
2	Moral dilemma discussions	1.23	0.12	Very low extent
3	Service to others	2.10	0.65	Low extent
4	Developmental discipline	0.53	0.77	Very low extent
5	Role modeling and mentoring	0.32	0.84	Very low extent
6	Nurturance	1.83	0.62	Very low extent
7	Trust and trustworthiness	2.30	0.76	Low extent
8	High expectations	1.74	0.69	Very low extent
9	School wide character focus	1.49	0.74	Very low extent
10	Family/community involvement	0.65	0.63	Very low extent
11	Pedagogy of empowerment	1.52	0.76	Very low extent
12	Teaching about character	2.72	0.85	High extent
13	Teaching social-emotional competence	1.46	0.59	Very low extent
14	Induction	0.95	0.87	Very low extent

Cluster mean score 1.41

Number of respondents 957

Benchmark score 2.50

Table I presents the mean rating of the extent to which research supported strategies are used in implementing values education in public secondary schools in Abia State. The table shows that out of the 14 items only one (item 12, $\bar{x}=2.72$) scored above the benchmark of 2.5. This implies that only the teaching about character is implemented to a high extent, all other strategies are implemented from low extent to very low extent. These include cooperative learning ($\bar{x}=0.90$), moral dilemma discussion ($\bar{x}=1.23$), service to others ($\bar{x}=2.10$), developmental discipline ($\bar{x}=0.53$), role modeling and mentoring ($\bar{x}=0.32$), nurturance ($\bar{x}=1.83$), trust and trustworthiness ($\bar{x}=2.30$). Others were high expectations ($\bar{x}=1.74$), school wide character focus ($\bar{x}=0.65$), family/community involvement ($\bar{x}=1.52$), teaching social-emotional competence ($\bar{x}=1.46$) and induction ($\bar{x}=0.95$). This implies that virtually all the research supported strategies of teaching values education are not utilized by value education teachers apart from teaching about character. The implication is that internalization of these values will be a bit difficult as they would be receiving the lesson as any other subject such as mathematics or geography. The students will never associate the lesson with its having impact on their lives. They would regard it as one of those lessons they need to read, pass and move on to the next class. The cluster mean which is 1.41 shows that the use of these strategies on the whole is very low. This means that there should be a great overhaul of the implementation process of values education in Abia State public secondary schools if the programme is expected to be effective and achieve its goal as noted by Berkowitz (2011).

4.2 Research Question 2: To what extent has values education implementation internalized honesty in students of public secondary schools in Abia State?

Table 2: Mean scores of respondents on the internalization of honesty among students of Abia State Public Secondary Schools through values education implementation

S/N	Items	X	SD	Decision
	To what extent do public secondary school students in Abia State:			
1	Own up to the offence they have committed.	1.06	0.71	Very low extent
2	Show willingness to report a culprit to the authorities.	1.14	0.64	Very low extent
3	Show the willingness to play by the rules at all times.	2.30	0.76	Low extent
4	Report facts the way they are without exaggerating.	2.37	0.82	Low extent
5	Always complain of something missing in the class.	2.74	0.75	High extent
6	Effortlessly tell lies to get out of trouble.	3.26	0.85	Very high extent

Cluster mean score 2.00

Number of respondents 957

Benchmark score 2.50

Table 2 shows that two items out of the six scored above the benchmark score of 2.5. These were items 6 and 5 which present students as effortlessly telling lies to get out of trouble ($\bar{x}=3.26$), and always complaining of something missing in the classroom ($\bar{x}=2.74$). Item 6 indicates a very high extent of lie telling while item 5 indicates a high extent of constant mission of students' possessions. The table also shows that four items (1, 2, 3, and 4) scored below the benchmark. Item 1 shows that students to a very low extent own up to any offence they have committed ($\bar{x}=1.06$), item 2 shows the students' low extent of reporting culprit to the authorities ($\bar{x}=1.14$) item 3 shows a low extent of the students effort to play by the rules at all times ($\bar{x}=2.30$). Item 4 also shows a low extent of the students' ability to report facts the way they are without exaggerating. The cluster mean score of 2.00 shown on the table indicates that internalization of honesty among the students is low. This low internalization of the value honesty could, be as a result of the strategy applied in the teaching of these values. It is also expected that the values should be reflected in the mission and visions of the schools while the parents and communities are involved. Virtually none of the research based strategies of implementing values education programmes visited is employed consequently the efforts put in by the teacher do not seem to have yielded the expected results.

4.3 Research Question 3: To what extent has values education implementation internalized compassion among students of public secondary schools in Abia State.

Table 3: Mean scores of respondents on the internalization of compassion among students of public secondary schools in Abia State

S/N	Items	$\bar{X}$	SD	Decision
	To what extent do public secondary school students in Abia State:			
1	Feel concerned about a classmate who lost a parent.	3.56	0.94	Very high extent
2	Feel ready to assist their classmates perform their class duty if not feeling well.	2.57	0.76	High extent
3	Show willingness to take home a sick classmate.	2.50	0.63	High extent
4	Give help to a physically challenged fellow student.	2.62	0.68	High extent
5	Treat junior students like younger ones.	2.34	0.71	Low extent
6	Reprimand prefects who are too harsh on fellow students.	2.42	0.69	Low extent
7	Condemn punishment that inflicts injury on students.	2.51	0.75	High extent

Cluster mean score 2.65

Number of respondents 957

Benchmark score 2.50

Table 3 shows that five out of the seven items have mean scores above that of the benchmark mean score of 2.5. Item 1 shows a very high extent of the students feeling concerned about a classmate that lost a parent ($\bar{x}=3.56$). Item 2 and 3 show a high extent of the students being ready to assist their classmates perform their duties when ill ($\bar{x}=2.57$) and a high extent of students' willingness to take home a sick classmate ($\bar{x}=2.50$) respectively. Items 4 and 7 also have mean scores above the benchmark mean score. Item 4 shows that the students are willing to help a physically challenged fellow student to a high extent ($\bar{x}=2.62$). Also the students are willing to condemn punishment that inflicts injury on students to a high extent ($\bar{x}=2.62$). However, the table also shows that the students to a low extent ($\bar{x}=2.34$) treat junior students as their younger ones. Item 6 also shows that the students to a low extent reprimand prefects who are too harsh on fellow students ($\bar{x}=2.41$). The explanation of these results is that either the strategy was effective on compassion or other forces outside the values education must be responsible for the students showing so much compassion. The students responded negatively to junior students and the prefects in items 5 and 6 because being senior secondary students they just want to rob it in that they are seniors and should be served while they protect the interest of their fellow seniors the prefects. The table shows a cluster mean of 2.65 which shows that the values education strategy employed to teach compassion was effective to a high extent. However, though not documented Nigerians are generally very compassionate people. They are ready to fight for the downtrodden in an unorganized way. This is more common in Abia State where if an innocent citizen is disposed of his or her belongings the bystanders often come to rescue the victim and lynch the culprit. It could be this feeling that played a role in this aspect.

4.4 Research Question 4: To what extent has values education implementation internalized respect among students of public secondary schools in Abia State?

Table 4: Mean scores of respondents on the internalization of respect among students of Abia State public secondary schools through values education implementation

S/N	Items	$\bar{X}$	SD	Decision
	To what extent do public secondary school students in Abia State:			
1	Greet their teachers any time they meet on the school compound.	2.42	0.65	Low extent
2	Offer to help their teachers carry any heavy load from them.	2.12	0.72	Low extent
3	Offer to help their senior students carry their bags.	2.23	0.80	Low extent
4	Get up for the senior students where the seats are inadequate.	2.50	0.78	High extent
5	Offer to clean a teacher's seat if it was not properly cleaned.	2.50	0.55	High extent
6	Suppress the eagerness to challenge a teacher who has accused them wrongly.	2.40	0.68	Low extent
7	Talk to teachers with respect.	2.51	0.52	High extent

Cluster mean score 2.38

Number of respondents 957

Benchmark score 2.50

Table 4 shows that items 4, 5 and 7 have mean scores above the benchmark mean score of 2.50. Item 4 shows that students to a high extent are willing to give up their seats to a senior where there is scarcity of seats ($\bar{x}=2.50$). Item 5 shows that students to a high extent talk to teachers with respect ($\bar{x}=2.51$). The table also shows that items 1,2,3 and 6 have mean scores below the benchmark score of 2.50. Item 1 indicates that students to a low extent find time to greet their teachers when they meet them on the school compound ($\bar{x}=2.42$). Item 2 indicates that students to a low extent help teachers with their heavy luggage ($\bar{x}=2.12$). Tables 3 and 6 indicate that students to a low extent are willing to help the seniors with their bags ($\bar{x}=2.23$) as well as suppress the eagerness to challenge a teacher who might have accused them wrongly ($\bar{x}=2.40$) respectively. The cluster mean score of 2.38 shows that the values education strategy employed in teaching respect was to a low extent effective. This can be explained by the non-employment of the research supported strategies for imparting values education in general despite success at subunit levels. Internalization of respect will go a long way to bring people in the secondary society if mutual respect is encouraged.

5. Implication of the Study to Theory and Practice

The findings of this study have some important implications to educational management and theory. The result which shows that only one out of the 14 research supported values education implementation strategies shows that there should be a total overhaul of the programme.

The result that shows out of the three constructs assessed only one yielded a positive response with the strategies being currently used. The cultural values should be comprehensively identified for standard curricula all over the state. The value education should be imparted compulsorily from kindergarten to secondary school level in order to lay strong values foundation. Evaluation of value education should not be academic rather it should be a routine one. Based on the daily observations of students, teachers and peers and should be monitored by the inspectorate division as well as parents to ensure character change.

Since values education has to do with human beings, it is believed that moral value is caught and not taught the teachers in charge of values education must be of very high moral standard, such that such a person should have the capacity to transform the students.

6. Conclusion

This study assessed values education strategies implementation and internalization of these values in the public secondary schools in Abia State. A list of research supported values education strategies were used to assess the implementation of values education in Abia State. Some values were also assessed to determine how effective the current strategy was to ensure internalization of those values. After analysis, implications of the study to educational theory and practice were recorded.

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